

DOLLAR TO EURO EXCHANGE RATE AND SOLAR ACTIVITY (1999–2025): $R^2=0.88$

V.A. Belkin

Abstract

This paper uses a methodological approach developed by W. S. Jevons and A. L. Chizhevsky. Solar cycle years were numbered according to the established order in solar astrophysics, grouped, and compared with the arithmetic mean values of Wolf numbers and changes in the dollar-euro exchange rate. The coefficient of determination in the diagram showing the ordinal numbers of solar cycle years and the dollar-euro exchange rate is 0.88.

The predicted dollar-euro exchange rate for 2026 is 1.11, for 2027 1.13, and for 2028 1.17.

Keywords

Dollar-euro exchange rate, solar cycles, Wolf numbers, economic cycles, foreign exchange market.

In his article “Solar-Commercial Cycles,” W. S. Jevons plotted solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760–1810 [1, P.227], that is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts the average solar activity cycle over a hundred years (the cycle of Wolf numbers) and the average cases of cholera in Russia for the years of the solar cycle for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

In this study, a single diagram compares the numbers of years of the average solar cycle, the values of Wolf numbers, and the dollar to euro exchange rate for the period 1999–2025.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity (SA), were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The ordinal numbers of years in column 3 of Table 1 are determined as follows. The first year in a SA cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, that is, the increase in the Wolf number, which is presented in column 2. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the SA minimum.

The St. Louis Federal Reserve website provides data on annual dollar-euro exchange rates for the period 1999-2025 [4]. These are presented in column 4 of Table 1.

Table 1. Average annual Wolf numbers, ordinal numbers of years in solar activity cycles and the dollar to euro exchange rate for 1999–2025

1. Years	2. Wolf number	3. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	4. Dollar to Euro exchange rate
1999	136.3	3	1.065
2000	173.9	4	0.923
2001	170.4	5	0.895
2002	163.6	6	0.945
2003	99.3	7	1.132
2004	65.3	8	1.244
2005	45.8	9	1.245
2006	24.7	10	1.256
2007	12.6	11	1.371
2008	4.2	12	1.473
2009	4.8	1	1.394
2010	24.9	2	1.326
2011	80.8	3	1.393
2012	84.5	4	1.286
2013	94	5	1.328
2014	113.3	6	1.330
2015	69.8	7	1.110
2016	39.8	8	1.107
2017	21.7	9	1.130
2018	7	10	1.182
2019	3.6	11	1.119

2020	8.8	1	1.141
2021	29.6	2	1.183
2022	83.2	3	1.053
2023	125.5	4	1.082
2024	154.6	5	1.082
2025	123.2	6	1.131
2026		7	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. Column 2 of Table 2 shows the number of such years for the period 1999–2025.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in solar activity cycles

1. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	2. Number of such years for the period 1999 – 2025	Arithmetic mean:	
		3. Wolf numbers	4. dollar to euro exchange rate
1	2	3	4
1	2	6.75	1.267
2	2	27.25	1.255
3	3	100.10	1.171
4	3	127.97	1.097
5	3	139.67	1.102
6	6	133.37	1.135
7	2	84.55	1.121
8	2	52.55	1.176
9	2	33.75	1.188

10	2	15.85	1.219
11	2	8.10	1.245
12	1	4.20	1.473
Total:	27		
Correlation coefficient: columns 3–4:			
lines 1– 11	25	-0.913	
lines 1– 12	27	-0.767	

Based on columns 1, 3, and 4 of Table 2, Fig. 1 is a diagram showing a strong correlation between the CA (average annual Wolf numbers) and the dollar/euro exchange rate by year of the average (12 years) CA cycle for 1999–2025. The determination coefficient value of 0.88 means that the constructed model explains 88% of the changes in the dollar/euro exchange rate. The significance level (p-value) is 0.0036 or $p < 0.01$. This means that the result is statistically significant at the classical academic level (reliability above 99%).

Fig. 1. Strong inverse relationship between Wolf numbers and the dollar/euro exchange rate by year of the average (12 years) SA cycle for 1999–2025, 27 years of observations, superposition method

The model in Fig. 1 can be used to forecast the dollar to euro exchange rate based on the known year number in the current SA cycle. For example, 2026 is the 7th year of the current 25th SA cycle (see Table 1) and in the diagram in Fig. 1 it corresponds to the forecast value of the dollar to euro exchange rate of 1.11. The ordinal number of the next year 2027 in the current SA cycle is 8 and in Fig. 1 it corresponds to the dollar to euro exchange rate of 1.13. The ordinal number of the year 2028 is 9 and in the diagram in Fig. 1 it corresponds to the dollar to euro exchange rate of 1.17. And so on.

The forecast of the Wolf number or year number in the current solar activity cycle can be determined based on data from the NASA website [5]. This forecast is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Forecast of the development of the current 25th cycle of solar activity

The scientific novelty of this study consists of the following:

1. A new research object: a cyclical relationship between the USD/EUR pair and SA cycles has been proven.
2. Record-breaking determination: the trend, purified using the superposition method, showed an abnormally high determination coefficient of $R^2 = 0.88$.
3. The author's forecasting method: the year number within the SA cycle served as an argument for the mathematical model.

This work does not constitute investment advice.

Reference

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